

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4b)

Progress of Excavation 27/II/80 R16A1: (4b) Removed with
trowel and brush. Toward center of deposit and R16A2 N
Balk becomes very thin - almost phased out. Consequently
some of frags shown in plan, and part samples, likely
include embedded in (4c). 2/II/80 R16A2: While (4b) looked to
be phasing out at R16A1 N Balk, proves to be substantial to N. Wall. When
picks up heavier concentration mortar, - 2-3 large embedded frags and
disintegrated in matrix. Mortar has differentiated from "gypsum" which
appears off-white to buff. Mortar looks more speckled white w/ pinkish tint or →

Locus Description "BUFF GYPSUM" Shows some granite, limestone
 Frags embedded in surface. Also seems a light ^{colored} clay-gypsum
 admixture

Location in Square _____

Under Locus (4a) COMPACT TAN CLAY Over Locus (4c) BROWN SAND WITH STONE RUBBLE

Locus Dimensions 8.21 - 8.15

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Few Alabaster, Dolerite, Granite
Frags (some from surface (4c)). 1 Large round limestone piece
embedded (see plan); med. to small limestone frags. Few small
sherd frags, all N.D.

fine red spots (flecks). Excavation shows large granite frags near or on surface (40). Some charcoal spots. 2-3 sherds, ND. Stone material after rifting fine to small to med. limestone frags. Largest Limestone Frag 13x7x10.